

Active fiber-loop method for improved performance assessment of Brillouin OTDR systems

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We report on what we believe to be a new fiber-optical measurement artifact used to assess the performance of Brillouin optical time-domain reflectometry (BOTDR) devices. In our proposed configuration, a fast optical switch is employed to significantly reduce the round-trip loss of a fiber loop probed by the BOTDR interrogator. Through a series of experiments, we demonstrate that our modified fiber artifact enables detailed characterization of BOTDR devices, allowing simultaneous assessment of distance-dependent spatial resolution, distance-dependent measurement biases, and system configuration anomalies. Our approach, which can be readily extended to other distributed optical fiber sensing modalities, provides a practical method for validating and benchmarking device performance. © 2025 Optica Publishing Group under the terms of the [Optica Open Access Publishing Agreement](#).

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Distributed optical fiber sensing (DOFS) is an increasingly popular method to passively monitor critical infrastructure such as high-voltage cables, tunnels, or other industrial assets [1,2]. The DOFS technology offers a unique method for spatially mapping physical quantities such as temperature, strain, and acoustic vibrations, over distances of tens of kilometers with resolutions on the order of a meter [3–5]. For temperature and strain sensing, Brillouin interrogators are widely used, as variations in these parameters induce local frequency shifts in the Brillouin backscattering spectrum [6–9]. Over the past decades, multiple Brillouin interrogator architectures have been developed, each employing different measurement approaches with their own strengths and limitations [10–13]. This diversity, however, complicates comparisons among devices that rely on the detection of extremely weak signals over a wide dynamic range.

Although DOFS is largely employed for applications related to critical infrastructure, the technology still lags behind in terms of metrologically grounded methods for performance assessment and validation. Fortunately, this aspect is now gaining attention with an increased focus on calibration protocols, traceable performance assessment, and standardization. For example, Christensen *et al.* recently proposed a new calibration method-

ology for BOTDR devices [14]. This approach builds upon established calibration procedures originally developed for Rayleigh optical time-domain reflectometry (OTDR) systems, offering a robust framework for enhancing measurement accuracy and traceability in fiber-optic sensing applications. The core idea is to use a fiber-optic artifact, consisting of a calibrated fiber loop, as a transfer standard which can be interrogated by the BOTDR device to be tested. With this approach, it becomes possible to detect distance-dependent measurement biases, assess accuracy, repeatability, and spatial resolution. For instance, sections of the fiber under test (FUT) can be put in a controlled environment and in different conditions (temperature, strain), under which the interrogator's performance can be evaluated as a function of distance. Reciprocally, the performance of the interrogator under temperature changes can be evaluated for quality insurance purposes.

In this Letter, we propose a modified and improved setup with lower overall loss, using an active optical switch to replace the 3-dB coupler of the original proposal in [14]. The improved loss budget of the modified active loop provides a two-fold improvement in the number of loop round-trips effectively measured by the interrogator device. This results in a more comprehensive performance evaluation, allowing better quantification of measurement accuracy, repeatability, and undesired distance-dependent measurement biases. We carry out three separate experiments that gauge the performance of a long-distance BOTDR interrogator similar to that of Ref. [15].

To put our work in perspective, we start by considering the fiber artifact setup proposed in [14], illustrated in Fig. 1(a). The fiber artifact consists of a 3-dB coupler connecting a lead-in fiber (length L_A) to a fiber loop (length L_B), including $L_{B_1} = 1040$ m and $L_{B_2} = 1600$ m. The input pulses enter the loop, and repetitively interrogate the FUT at each round-trip. In the first pass through the FUT (L_{B_1}), the pump pulse has already experienced 3 dB of loss since half of the power is redirected to the ended coupler output. Moreover, the backscattering signal experiences 3 dB of loss when returning to the interrogator.

The loss budget for one round-trip is strictly greater than 3 dB, and typically on the order of $l_{rt} = 4.5$ dB, as illustrated in Fig. 1(b). Note that this plot scales the losses by a factor of two to depict the one-way attenuation losses of the FUT. The large round-trip loss of the fiber loop in the configuration of Ref. [14]

Fig. 1. (a) Experimental setup of [14]. L_{B1} is the fiber segment sensed at every round-trip. The backscattering signal from L_{B2} is blocked at the isolator. This configuration requires $L_{B2} > L_{B1}$ to prevent spatial ambiguity of the return signal. (b) OTDR measurement from the interrogator, showing a round-trip loss of 4.5 dB.

limits the data acquisition to 4 round-trips, which limits the ability to statistically assess the distance-dependent performance of BOTDR devices. The equivalent interrogation distance for each round-trip is not trivially mapped to the loss budget, because the backscattering signal always travels the same distance to the interrogator, independently of the round-trip number. For the first round-trip, the loss experienced by the pump pulses and the backscattering signal are similar, and the corresponding interrogation distance is 15 km, assuming a one-way loss $\alpha_{dB} = 0.2$ dB/km. For that round-trip loss, the fiber is interrogated at intervals of about 22.5 km. Reducing the loss budget of the fiber loop l_{rt} is also helpful to assess the performance of interrogators at shorter intervals and from a closer distance.

The proposed modified setup replaces the 3 dB coupler with a fast polarization-insensitive optical switch (Agiltron NSSW-125111333, 100 ns rise time), as shown in Fig. 2(a). An additional 90/10 tap coupler is added after the ignored fiber $L_{B2} \approx 1650$ m to detect the arrival of the pump pulse. The optical switch path is briefly changed to let the pulse propagate in the FUT, and then switches back to its initial position so that the backscattering signal reaches the interrogator. To do so, an electrical “one-shot” pulse generator is used (Analog Devices LTC6993). When the optical pulse is detected at the photodiode, the optical switch changes path for a duration of $t_s = 1 \mu\text{s}$. This time gate is long enough for BOTDR pump pulses, which usually do not exceed 500 ns, for a spatial resolution of 50 m. It is also sufficient to allow the propagation of a pulse train when the interrogator is used with 7-bits return to zero-pulse coding [16]. The delay fiber $L_{B3} \approx 105$ m ensures that the optical pulse is synchronized with the electrical trigger of the switch. The detection of electronics induces a lag of about 350 ns. Depending on the timing of the gate opening and passing of the pump pulse, a small part of the FUT is not measured as the backscattering signal is redirected clock-wise in the loop and blocked by the isolator. The corresponding OTDR trace is shown in Fig. 2(b). A reflection caused by the imperfect switch isolation as well as some jitter due to the switch transition can be observed at each round-trip. The number of round-trips is limited by the dynamic range of the photodetector (JDSU X07051650), triggering the optical switch. Therefore, the backscattering signal is then strictly blocked, giving a lower bound for the repetition rate of the interrogator. In our experiments, up to 10 round-

Fig. 2. (a) Improved experimental setup. The segment $L_{B1} \approx 1050$ m is sensed at every round-trip. A fraction of the pump pulse is extracted and amplified with an erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) to detect the incoming pump pulse and trigger the optical switch. Dashed lines indicate an electrical link. This configuration requires $L_{B2} + L_{B3} > L_{B1}$. (b) OTDR measurement from the interrogator, showing a round-trip loss of 3.2 dB. (c) Subset of the trigger signal as seen by a fast photodiode (PD) at integers of the loop round-trip time.

trips could be observed. Figure 2(c) depicts a signal similar to that seen by the one-shot pulse detector. Its intensity diminishes rapidly as a result of the intra-loop losses. Acquiring the signal at 3.2 GSamples/s for 1 second (Spectrum Instrumentation M5i.3321) confirmed that the optical switch is reliably triggered for over 4500 continuous interrogation pulses. Figure 2(b) indicates a round-trip loss of 3.2 dB, showing the first 8 round-trips.

The performance of both the passive- and active loop setups is compared in terms of Brillouin backscattering intensity in Fig. 3. The response curves, calculated as an integral under the Brillouin line spectrum (BLS), indicate that the modified setup nearly doubles the number of round-trips for the same loss budget. The equivalent interrogation distance for the first round-trip corresponds to the insertion losses of the switch, of about 1 dB, which corresponds to 5 km. The next round-trips add a 3.2 dB loss, which corresponds to a 16 km measurement interval for the pump pulse. The proposed configuration is readily used to reveal potential distance-dependent spatial resolution or biases. The interrogator used for the following measurements operates as the one of Ref. [15], stepping through the frequencies that cover the BLS and acquiring the backscattering signal via heterodyne detection. A peak-fitting routine determines the central position of the BLS. In Fig. 4, the position of the frequency peak is observed for each round-trip at a fixed spatial position in a fiber segment heated to 35°C and 50°C.

To illustrate the possibility of detecting distance-dependent biases, a peak fitting routine with fixed peak width is used. The

Fig. 3. Brillouin loss budget for the setup of [14] and the proposed active configuration. Backscattering intensities originating from the ignored fiber are replaced with a straight line. Round-trip loss is ≈ 4.3 dB for the passive configuration, versus ≈ 2.9 dB for the active configuration. The initial loss difference is of 2 dB.

Fig. 4. Peak frequency as a function of the round-trip number for (a) 2 m spatial resolution, (b) 8 m spatial resolution. In the case of (b), bias is introduced by the fixed-width peak fit routine. The error bars depict the variations of the measurand for neighboring positions that are expected to be at the same temperature.

FUT is a standard SMF-28 fiber whose BLS features a dominant peak as well as a weaker secondary peak. Two measurement series are performed, with different spatial resolutions. When the spatial resolution is high (2 m), the BLS is broad and strictly single-peaked [17]. No systematic error is observed when the interrogator has a spatial resolution of 2 m, as depicted in Fig. 4(a). At a lower spatial resolution of 8 m, the BLS is narrower, and a tiny secondary peak appears. When the backscattering signal becomes weaker with distance, that secondary peak tends to diminish and gradually vanish in the noise floor. This also leads to a narrowing of the BLS. A fixed-width peak fitting routine is not insensitive to changes in spectral shape, potentially leading to a bias, manifested as a slight increase in peak fit frequency with distance, as depicted in Fig. 4(b).

In a second experiment, the FUT is locally heated to 40°C on a segment length of 1 m, and the measured temperature in the peak of that hotspot is observed over a set of 90 measurements with a spatial resolution of 10 m. Changes in peak position of the BLS are observed across 8 round-trips, and the repeatability is calculated and compared to that of a > 10 m segment at 20°C. Hotspots shorter than the spatial resolution are known to be dif-

Fig. 5. Standard deviation (std. dev.) of the BLS peak position (a) within a hotspot, (b) at room temperature across 90 measurements, as a function of the round-trip number.

Fig. 6. Fiber under test and its hotspot series for the first five round-trips (RT), with a spatial resolution of 2 m.

icult to resolve, because most of the information contained in the BLS comes from neighboring spatial positions at lower temperature. Figures 5(a) and 5(b) depict the standard deviation of the BLS peak frequency position in the middle of the hotspot and in a segment at 20°C, respectively. The repeatability is better in that segment, indicating that the performance of the device is not only position dependent, but also affected by temperature or strain events smaller than the spatial resolution. In this experiment, no attempt is made to increase the spatial resolution of the system [18,19], but this setup would be appropriate to discover the limits of such methods.

In a third experiment, the distance-dependency of the spatial resolution is measured at heated subsections of the loop fiber. The interrogator is configured with a pulse duration of 20 ns (2 m spatial resolution), with and without pulse coding [16], and the hotspots are 23°C warmer than room temperature. Figure 6 depicts the hotspot series of sizes 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 10, 15, 20, 30, and 60 m, for the first five round-trips.

To quantitatively gauge the spatial resolution of the BOTDR interrogator, we investigate the step response of the Brillouin frequency (measurand) for each of the sharp temperature steps connected to hotspots illustrated in Fig. 6 with a length exceeding 4 m (hotspots 4–10). The spatial resolution, z_{res} , is defined as a 90-% step coverage, and is quantified for each sub-trace by fitting an error function of the form $f(z|A, B, z_0, z_{res}) = A + B \operatorname{erf}[2.33(z - z_0)/z_{res}]$ to data points in the close vicinity of the step [20]. A select subset (rounds 1 and 4) of the interrogator step response, and the corresponding error-function fits, are visualized in Fig. 7(a). The same subset obtained using 7-bit pulse coding is seen in Fig. 7(b). Each sub-plot contains both the positive (black dots) and the negative step (green circles) of a given hotspot, and the fitted value of the spatial resolution is appended as $s_{u,d}$.

Fig. 7. (a) Measurement of the spatial resolution of the system with 20 ns pump pulses, for hotspots 4 to 10. (b) Same, when pulse coding is used. The y-axis represents the Brillouin frequency shift, whose values are omitted for clarity.

Table 1. Estimation of the Spatial Resolution of the System^a

	$\hat{z}_{res}^{(1)}/m$	$\hat{z}_{res}^{(2)}/m$	$\hat{z}_{res}^{(3)}/m$	$\hat{z}_{res}^{(4)}/m$
Steps ↑	2.29(0.09)	2.43(0.13)	2.33(0.19)	2.21(0.23)
Steps ↓	2.10(0.07)	2.10(0.12)	2.22(0.14)	2.36(0.48)
Steps ↑ + ↓	2.20(0.07)	2.26(0.12)	2.27(0.11)	2.28(0.23)
Steps ↑	3.29(0.14)	3.31(0.19)	3.46(0.21)	3.22(0.42)
Steps ↓	3.01(0.13)	3.09(0.26)	3.12(0.22)	2.90(0.41)
Steps ↑ + ↓	3.15(0.12)	3.20(0.15)	3.29(0.16)	3.06(0.27)

^aThe estimate of the spatial resolution $\hat{z}_{res}^{(i)}$, versus the loop round-trip i , using 20-ns probe pulses from the interrogator. The upper rows represent results without pulse coding, while the lower rows represent results with pulse coding. Values in parentheses represent standard uncertainties, e.g., 2.30(0.04) m is shorthand notation for (2.30 ± 0.04) m.

With the outlined method, we obtain 14 measurements of z_{res} per round-trip in the loop, providing a robust data basis for estimating \hat{z}_{res} . Our full analysis, separated into individual round-trips and partly distinguishing between positive and negative steps, is summarized in Table 1. The results indicate a non-negligible loss in spatial resolution due to the use of pulse coding, due to EDFA saturation, leading to unequal pulse peak power within one code, and a residual continuous optical signal due to a limited modulation depth [21]. In addition, we observe a small asymmetry between the up and down steps, the origin of which is currently unknown.

In this work, we have developed and demonstrated a low-loss fiber-optical artifact for the performance evaluation of BOTDR devices. Compared with previous work, the improved loss budget of our approach enables a significantly improved assessment of distance-dependent measurement biases and spatial resolution. The proposed active configuration is relatively

straightforward to implement and, as we demonstrate, is fully compatible with characterizing and evaluating the performance of advanced techniques such as pulse coding. Our setup provides a practical platform for the calibration and performance evaluation of BOTDR devices and may, with minor modifications, be extended to other time-domain sensing modalities, including Raman OTDR and BOTDA [22].

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

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